

Local Government in Germany

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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1. The System of Local Government in Germany

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Types of Local Governments

In Germany, government at the local level is administered through municipalities (*Gemeinden*) as well as second-tier local governments such as counties (*Kreise*). Larger municipalities with more than 100,000 citizens are often assigned the status of independent city or county-free city (*kreisfreie Stadt*); in addition to their municipality responsibilities, these cities also carry out (second-tier) county responsibilities. In some of the German *Länder*, there are even third-tier local governments, for example districts (*Bezirke*) in Bavaria.¹ There are no areas that fall directly under federal or *Länder* rule, as the system of local government extends to the entire territory of the country. However, as jurisdiction over the organizational powers of local authorities lies with each of the 16 *Länder*, 'local government' may come in different shapes. This is particularly true for its internal organization, but may equally be said of its precise powers and responsibilities. Nevertheless, there are several common features of local government.

The German concept of local self-government, as enshrined in Article 28(2) of the Basic Law, implies that local government entities have a general competence (*Allzuständigkeit*) to carry out all responsibilities that are relevant to the local community. Since this general competence is comprehensive, there is, as a result, no such thing as single purpose local governments in Germany. This means that local governments in Germany may, for instance, run public libraries, museums, theaters, opera houses or concert halls, that they can provide airport facilities, energy/water supply, waste/sewage disposal, run hospitals, kindergarten facilities or homes for the elderly. Of course, these vast competences do not go unchecked; local authorities may engage in such activities only within their financial capacity and, in all their activities, local authorities have to abide by the laws and limitations of federal and *Länder* legislation. Nevertheless, contrary to the Anglo-Saxon concept of 'ultra-vires'², local authorities do not act illegally if they take measures in areas that do not fall within responsibilities explicitly transferred to them by federal or state legislation. In view of their general competence, they just need not to be empowered specifically to take action at the local level.

¹ For these and the following considerations see Martin Burgi, 'Federal Republic of Germany' in Nico Steytler (ed), *Local Government and Metropolitan Regions in Federal Systems* (McGill-Queen's University Press 2009) 140-142.

² See Veith Mehde, 'Steering, Supporting, Enabling: The Role of Law in Local Government Reforms' (2006) 28 *Law & Policy* 164, 165.

Legal Status of Local Governments

The right of local governments to self-government (i.e. to carry out all responsibilities falling within their ‘general competence’) is constitutionally enshrined at the federal level in Article 28(2) of the Basic Law (BL).³ This provision reads as follows: ‘Within the limits prescribed by law, municipalities shall be guaranteed the right to regulate all local affairs in their own responsibility. Within the limits of their responsibilities as defined by law, associations of municipalities shall equally have the right of self-government according to the laws. The guarantee of self-government shall include the basis of financial autonomy; it shall comprise the right of municipalities to a source of tax revenues that corresponds with the economic ability of the tax debtors (e.g. business tax – *Gewerbesteuer*), and the right to fix the rates at which these sources shall be taxed.’ Provisions similar to Article 28(2) BL are also contained in the constitutions of the 16 *Länder* which thus reinforce the constitutional recognition of local authorities and their right to self-government. The constitutional recognition of local government is generally the same for all municipalities, regardless of size or socio-economic importance.

In contrast, the constitutional standing of counties and districts is weaker. Compared to the comprehensive self-government of their constituent municipalities, these second- and third-tier local government entities may not carry out all responsibilities of local importance but are granted the right to self-government only ‘within the limits of their responsibilities as defined by law’ (Article 28(2) BL).

It is important to stress that Article 28(2) BL as well as the corresponding constitutional provisions at *Länder* level do not grant local autonomy as an absolute right. Local autonomy is only guaranteed in principle, while its precise scope is subject to legislation. Thus, it is the lawmakers at federal and *Länder* level that define the precise extent and limitations of local self-government. In practice, the sheer volume of (sometimes very detailed) federal and *Länder* statutes has considerably limited local autonomy. However, as local autonomy is constitutionally guaranteed in principle, local governments are protected by virtue of Article 28(2) BL against excessive and immoderate restrictions of local autonomy and preserves a ‘core sphere’ (*Kernbereich*) of responsibilities that must remain with municipalities (i.e. finances, local planning, personnel matters, organizational autonomy and the freedom to engage in joint administration with neighboring communities). In addition to that, Article 28(2) BL protects local authorities, to some extent, against the revocation of responsibilities (*Aufgabenentzug*) e.g. by reallocating them at a higher (more centralized) administrative level (*Hochzonung*). As a result, only *very substantial* gains in cost-efficiency, for instance, may justify that responsibilities are taken away from local governments.

³ See Burgi, *Federal Republic of Germany*, above, 143-146.

(A) Symmetry of the Local Government System

As pointed out, the legal status is primarily the same for all municipalities regardless of their size and socio-economic importance, although larger municipalities (and especially independent cities) have, with no doubt, more political bearing. As a general principle, the German system follows a symmetrical approach towards the legal status of local governments. However, this symmetry of responsibilities de jure can be modified in various ways which may result, de facto, in an asymmetrical allocation of responsibilities.

Local authorities may, for example, agree among themselves to join forces and create joint administrative units to carry out specific responsibilities in forms of what is called inter-municipal cooperation (*interkommunale Zusammenarbeit*). For instance, they may, with regard to capacity and cost-effectiveness, share their resources and establish a joint inter-municipal corporation (*Zweckverband*) which is assigned to take care of sewage and/or waste disposal. Such cooperation is particularly common between smaller municipalities but are equally practiced within larger conurbations and between counties and independent cities.

Because of their size, independent cities are capable of carrying out both municipal and county responsibilities through their city administration as a single unit. In rural areas, by contrast, county responsibilities are carried out by counties along with their constituent (smaller) municipalities. The precise division of duties between counties and their municipalities is laid down in *Länder* statutes and may therefore vary. As a general rule, the allocation of responsibilities depends on the capacities of the individual local unit. This means that for reasons of administrative efficiency, counties will regularly assume the execution of duties that cannot be effectively handled by their constituent municipalities. For instance, hospitals will usually be run at county (or even district) level while minor administrative duties such as citizen registration may remain with the constituent municipalities.

Political and Social Context in Germany

Despite the recent turbulences in the course of the financial and migration crises, the political system established under the Basic Law has proven to be relatively stable. In the overall perspective, two parties, the Christian Democrats (CDU/CSU) and the Social Democrats (SPD) still each win between 20 to 40 per cent of total votes while four smaller parties, the Liberal Free Democrats (FDP), the Greens (*Bündnis 90/Die Grünen*), the Left Party (*Die Linke*) and the Alternative for Germany (AfD), attract between 5 and 20 per cent of all voters. In the East German 'new' *Länder*, *Die Linke* and AfD are usually stronger in elections than in West Germany. On the *Länder* level and on the local level, the landscape of political parties is more diverse. In addition to the aforementioned parties, there are several parties which are particularly active in certain regions and municipalities, taking account of political issues with specific relevance for the respective region or municipality. In Bavaria, for example, the

Independent Voters (Freie Wähler) are usually quite strong in the elections – they won 11,6 per cent of the votes during the 2018 elections for the Bavarian *Landtag* and are hence currently part of the Bavarian government, and they are represented in numerous municipal councils.

The spatial distribution of the population still reflects, to a certain extent, the decentralized structure of the Federal Republic of Germany. 27 per cent of the population (i.e. around 22 million people) live in smaller municipalities with 5,000 – 20,000 inhabitants. Another 27 per cent live in medium sized cities (*Mittelstädte*) with 20,000 – 100,000 inhabitants. 31 per cent of the German population live in major cities (*Großstädte*) with more than 100,000 inhabitants. The largest cities with more than 1,000,000 inhabitants each are Berlin (3,700,000), Hamburg (1,890,000), Munich (1,470,000) and Cologne (1,080,000). Of course, many smaller municipalities and medium sized cities are part of a metropolitan area (*Ballungsraum*). Together with Böblingen (50,000), Waiblingen (55,000), Sindelfingen (64,000), Tübingen (89,000), Ludwigsburg (93,000) and Esslingen (93,000), for instance, Reutlingen (115,000), Heilbronn (123,000) and Stuttgart (634,000) as well as all surrounding municipalities form the Stuttgart metropolitan area (total population: 5,300,000). In this perspective, around 77 per cent of the German population nowadays live in metropolitan regions.

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